

StanleyLandmarkDH

KS13H9xSYMOnumentDH

145 doubled haploid lines

38 doubled haploid lines

Normal: 66 (45.5%)

Abnormal: 79 (54.5%)

Normal: 21 (55.3%)

Abnormal: 17 (44.7%)

86 primary DH lines
with ≥ 2 DH_{0:1} progeny

1-6 DH_{0:1} seeds per line
(DH line scored based on
DH_{0:1} progeny)

3-5 DH_{0:1} seeds per line
(DH line scored based on
DH_{0:1} progeny)

396 DH_{0:1} plants

187 DH_{0:1} plants

Normal: 242 (61%)

Abnormal: 154 (39%)

Normal: 155 (83%)

Abnormal: 32 (17%)

DH_{0:1} progenies:

26 primary DH (30.2%): normal + abnormal

39 primary DH (45.4%): all normal

21 primary DH (24.4%): all abnormal

Total aberrations: 239

Aneuploidy: 81

Deletion: 114

Translocation/Duplication: 44

DH_{0:1} with the

specific aberration:

17% (66)

24% (95)

9% (37)

Total aberrations: 40

Aneuploidy: 28

Deletion: 4

Translocation/Duplication: 8

DH_{0:1} with the

specific aberration:

12% (22)

2% (4)

4% (8)

After sub-genome length normalization
to 5Gbp, aberrations in sub-genomes:

A sub-genome: 28.36%

B sub-genome: 28.54%

D sub-genome: 43.10%

After sub-genome length normalization
to 5Gbp, aberrations in sub-genomes:

A sub-genome: 15.62%

B sub-genome: 25.56%

D sub-genome: 58.82%

47 DH_{0:1} selfed to generate DH_{1:2} generation

19 normal DH_{0:1}: all normal DH_{1:2} progeny

9 normal DH_{0:1}: at least one abnormal DH_{1:2} progeny

19 abnormal DH_{0:1}: segregation of aberrations in DH_{1:2} progeny

Supplementary Fig. S6: Summary of chromosomal aberrations in StanleyLandmarkDH and KS13H9xSYMOnumentDH populations.